

Glossary

MOTHER EARTH MSCA POSTDOCTORAL FELLOWSHIP

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Introduction

This glossary is a helpful guide to understanding some important words and ideas used in this project. Sometimes these words can be confusing or mean different things in different places.

We provide these definitions to help you understand what we mean when we use certain terms. You may have a different definition based on your culture, society or country. Here, we are sharing the concepts that guided the way we use these words in this project.

To do this, we have used definitions from international law as a starting point.

The glossary focuses on four key terms:

- Indigenous Peoples;
- Maroon Communities/Afro-descendant Communities;
- Environmental Degradation;
- Cultural Rights, including biocultural rights and bio-socio-cultural approach.

This glossary is meant to give a starting point. It provides **tentative definitions** that can guide discussions, help communities understand their rights, and support actions to protect their lands, cultures, and environment.

Indigenous People

Indigenous People

When we talk about Indigenous peoples, there isn't one perfect definition that everyone agrees on. Indigenous cultures are diverse, each with their own traditions, languages, and ways of life. Even the words communities use to describe themselves can be different:

first nations

indigenous peoples

aboriginal peoples

and many others

Each Indigenous group decides for itself who they are, thus, we're going to look at the legal definition. This can be helpful when talking about legal issues.

The United Nations often uses a definition from José Martínez Cobo. He described Indigenous communities as groups with a strong, long-standing connection to the people who lived in a region before colonisation. These communities see themselves as different from the societies in power today.

ILO

An important definition comes from the International Labour Organization (ILO) Convention, No. 169. It describes Indigenous peoples in independent countries as groups whose ancestors lived in the country or region before it was colonised or conquered. These communities, no matter their legal status, still keep some or all of their own ways of living, including social, economic, cultural and political traditions.

The ILO definition has two main parts:

Objective element: Facts like having a long history in the region, a connection to their ancestral land, and keeping their unique ways of life.

Subjective element: This is about self-identification: Indigenous peoples have the right to identify themselves as Indigenous and be recognized as such by others.

And what about a national definition?

This project focuses on Brazil and Colombia. Both countries have ratified and agreed to follow ILO Convention 169. Because of this, when we talk about the legal definition of Indigenous peoples in these countries, the international definition from this Convention often guides how Indigenous peoples are recognised.

At the same time, both Brazil and Colombia also have their own national legal definitions of Indigenous peoples, which should be used alongside the international definition.

It should be noted that the self-declaration still is the most important criteria for International, Brazilian and Colombian law.

Brazil

Colombia

Brazil

In Brazil's law, called the Indian Statute, an Indigenous person is defined as:

“any individual of pre-Columbian origin and ancestry who identifies and is identified as belonging to an ethnic group whose cultural characteristics distinguish them from the national society.” (Article 3(I)).

For Indigenous communities, it defined them as:

“a group of Indigenous families or communities, either living in complete isolation from other sectors of the national community, or in intermittent or permanent contact with them, without however being integrated into them.” (Art. 3(II))

The Superior Tribunal Federal, using the definition of the ILO Convention has declared that:

“The identity of a group as an indigenous people is, first and foremost, a matter subject to self-recognition by the members of the group itself.” (Constitutional Court of Brazil, ADPF n° 709 MC-Ref)

Colombia

In Colombia, a legal definition is stipulated by the Decree 2001 of 1988. It says Indigenous Peoples are:

“group of families of Amerindian descent who share feelings of identification with their aboriginal past, maintaining traits and values characteristic of their traditional culture, as well as forms of internal government and social control that distinguish them from other rural communities.” (Article 2 of the Decree 2001 of 1988)

The Constitutional Court of Colombia has also recognised that:

“The right to self-identification of indigenous communities and their members is a manifestation of the right to cultural identity recognised both in national legislation and in Article 1.2 of ILO Convention 169. This right guarantees the autonomy of communities to define themselves, recognise their members and preserve their cultural identity... as an autonomous right that imposes duties on the State..” (Corte Constitucional of Colombia, Sentencia T-185/25).

**Maroon
Communities
&
Afro-
descendant
Communities**

Maroon Communities

Maroon communities, often called Quilombolas in Brazil and Palenqueros in Colombia, are groups of people of African descent who have preserved their own social, cultural, and economic traditions.

quilombola

palenqueros

Many of these communities were originally formed by people who escaped slavery, and in countries like Brazil and Colombia, the government also recognises communities created by freed or formerly enslaved people with the official status of protected community (**Afro-Descendant Communities**).

Although they are not always indigenous to the regions where they live, these communities remain distinct from other parts of the national population, maintaining their unique identity and traditions.

In international law, they are referred to as tribal peoples. They are protected by the ILO Convention 169, which defines tribal people as:

ILO tribal peoples in independent countries whose social, cultural and economic conditions distinguish them from other sections of the national community, and whose status is regulated wholly or partially by their own customs or traditions or by special laws or regulations.

It can be difficult to precisely define these communities, but two main things help us identify them:

Shared Way of Life: These communities often have unique social, cultural, and economic practices that distinguish them. They might have their own customs, traditions, and ways of life, sometimes even regulating themselves through their own norms. They often have a special connection to the land they live on, which can include traditional ways of owning and using land.

Self-Identification: Members of these communities see themselves as part of a distinct group with a shared identity, history, and worldview different from other parts of the population.

And what about a national definition?

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At the same time, both Brazil and Colombia also have their own national legal definitions, which should be used alongside the international definition.

Brazil

Colombia

Brazil

In Brazil, quilombos represent diverse forms of autonomous territorial occupation, which developed from various circumstances beyond just runaway enslaved Africans, and whose identity is deeply rooted in ancestral traditions and cultural practices.

According to the Decree 4887 of 2003, quilombolas are:

“ethnic-racial groups, according to self-attribution criteria, with their own historical trajectory, endowed with specific territorial relations, with presumed black ancestry related to resistance to historical oppression suffered.”

Colombia

For Colombia, ILO has analysed the application of the Convention 169 for NARP, not only palenquero communities. Thus, it can be argued that Colombia should apply this convention to all NARP communities.

Furthermore, in 2003, the Colombian Constitutional Court interpreted the International Labour Organization's Convention 169 in a broad way, extending its protections to **comunidades negras** as well as Indigenous and tribal peoples. This decision highlighted how the ways of life of these communities are deeply connected to their lands and to the use, care, and management of natural resources (Constitutional Court, Sentencia T-955 de 2003).

The Court emphasized that protecting ethnic and cultural diversity is essential for the survival of Indigenous, tribal, and comunidades negras, and that these communities play a key role in maintaining Colombia's multi-ethnic and multicultural identity.

comunidades negras

“It is the group of families of Afro-Colombian descent who have their own culture, share a history and have their own traditions and customs within the rural-urban relationship, which reveal and preserve an awareness of identity that distinguishes them from other ethnic groups.”

(Art. 2 of Ley 70 de 1993)

comunidades afrocolombianas

“These are human groups present throughout the national territory (urban and rural), with African historical, ethnic and cultural roots and ancestry, born in Colombia, with their racial, linguistic and folkloric diversity.”

References:

Gobierno de Colombia, Unidad para las víctimas, available at <<https://www.unidadvictimas.gov.co/comunidades-negras-afrocolombianas-raizales-y-palenqueras/>>.

comunidades raizales

“They are the native population of the islands of San Andrés, Providencia and Santa Catalina, descendants of the union between Europeans (mainly English, Spanish and Dutch) and African slaves. They are distinguished by their culture, language (Creole), religious beliefs (Baptist Church) and historical past similar to that of Antillean peoples such as Jamaica and Haiti. Given their cultural specificity, they have been the subject of socio-cultural policies, plans and programmes that differ from those of other black communities on the Colombian mainland.”

comunidades palenqueras

“The Palenque community is made up of the descendants of enslaved people who, through acts of resistance and freedom, took refuge in the territories of the northern coast of Colombia from the 15th century onwards, known as palenques.”

References:

Gobierno de Colombia, Unidad para las víctimas, available at <<https://www.unidadvictimas.gov.co/comunidades-negras-afrocolombianas-raizales-y-palenqueras/>>.

Environmental degradation

What is Environmental Degradation?

According to the General Multilingual Environmental Thesaurus (used by the European Environment Agency), environmental degradation means any process that harms the natural environment, reducing biodiversity and the overall health of nature. This can happen naturally, but it is often caused or worsened by human activities.

The United Nations Office for Disaster Risk Reduction (UNDRR) explains that environmental degradation happens when nature loses its ability to support people and ecosystems. It can also make natural disasters like floods, droughts, and fires more frequent or intense.

In this project, we focus on environmental degradation caused by human actions and how it affects communities, especially Indigenous and Maroon peoples.

References:

European Environment Agency / Eionet. GEMET – General Multilingual Environmental Thesaurus, Concept.

United Nations Office for Disaster Risk Reduction. 2009 UNISDR Terminology on Disaster Risk Reduction. PreventionWeb, 2009.

natural environment

The natural environment includes everything that exists without human influence — the land, water, air, plants, animals, and even outer space.

What type of human activities?

Human activities that cause environmental degradation may include:

- Misuse of land and soil erosion;
- Deforestation and loss of biodiversity;
- Desertification and wildfires;
- Pollution of land, water, and air;
- Climate change and rising sea levels...

Cultural Rights

Cultural Rights

There is no single, official definition of cultural rights. Different disciplines, such as cultural studies, anthropology and legal studies, understand culture in multiple ways: as a product, as a process, and as a way of life. This broad understanding means that culture goes far beyond ethnicity, language or religion. It includes the many practices, meanings, values, expressions and forms of knowledge through which individuals and communities live.

way of life

practices

values

among others.

Reference:
Report of the independent expert in the field of cultural rights, Ms.
Farida Shaheed, submitted pursuant to resolution 10/23 of the
Human Rights Council, UN Doc.: A/HRC/14/36, 22 March 2010.

One interesting definition is given by Alassane N'Daw :

“Culture comprises all forms of expression, thought and action peculiar to a given community. It includes the beliefs, institutions and techniques which impose the same style of living on the members of a society. It ensures the unity and stability, while undergoing the transformations, of that society-transformations to which moreover it continually contributes”.

“Concluding, we would say that cultural activity is the materialization of the creative aspirations and capacities latent in all people. The cultural rights of a people mainly involve the power to maintain, revive, develop and make known its own values”.

Reference:
Alassane N'Daw, “Universal culture and national cultures” in
UNESCO, Cultural rights as human rights, Paris, 1970.
UNESCO Doc.: SHC.68/XIX.3/A

In international law, cultural rights are grounded in major human rights treaties. Both the International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights (ICCPR) and the International Covenant on Economic, Social and Cultural Rights (ICESCR) affirm the right of everyone to take part in cultural life.

**art. 27 of
ICCPR**

**art. 15 of
ICESCR**

The Committee on Economic, Social and Cultural Rights, in its General Comment No. 21 (2009), highlights that cultural life is “a living process, historical, dynamic and evolving” (para. 11). It stresses that culture should not be seen as isolated traditions or fixed elements, but as an interactive process through which individuals and communities express themselves while maintaining their distinct identities and contributing to the shared culture of humanity (para. 12).

Additional clarification is offered by the Fribourg Declaration on Cultural Rights, which identifies a set of cultural rights relating to:

**identity and
cultural
heritage**

**freedom to identify
with one or more
communities**

**access to and
participation
in cultural life**

**education and
training**

**information
and
communication**

**cultural
cooperation**

Here, we will focus on the right to take part in cultural life.

International human rights bodies generally describe the right to participate in cultural life as having three interrelated components:

**participation in
cultural life**

**access to cultural
life**

**contribution to
cultural life**

This right also includes the right not to participate in cultural activities or expressions.

Approaches developed by **indigenous peoples** contribute further insight by emphasising a holistic and all-inclusive view of culture.

Indigenous peoples approaches offer particularly important perspectives on cultural rights. Their approaches highlight that culture is not a separate sphere of life but a holistic, interdependent system that includes land, language, spirituality, governance, modes of subsistence, knowledge systems, and relationships with the natural world. In many Indigenous worldviews, these elements cannot be isolated from one another: caring for land is also caring for culture; protecting language is safeguarding identity; maintaining traditional governance is ensuring the continuity of collective life.

International instruments such as the **UN Declaration on the Rights of Indigenous Peoples (UNDRIP)** reinforce these understandings by recognising Indigenous peoples' rights to maintain, control, protect and develop their cultural heritage and traditional knowledge, and to uphold their own cultural institutions and ways of life.

As for Maroon Communities and Afro-descendant communities, important considerations for cultural rights. Their cultural identities and governance systems have historically been shaped by resistance, self-determination, and close relationships with specific territories. Yet, like many other African-descendant and tribal peoples, Maroon communities are under-recognised in international law: their cultural rights are generally addressed only through broad instruments, such as the ICCPR and ICESCR, rather than through tailored standards that reflect their particular histories, collective identities and land-based cultural practices.

And what about a national definition?

This project focuses on Brazil and Colombia. Both countries also have their own national legal definitions, which should be used alongside the international definition.

Brazil

Colombia

Brazil

Cultural rights were included in Brazil's 1988 Constitution, even though the Constitution does not give a precise definition of what they are. Instead, it sets out a series of principles and responsibilities that guide how the State must protect and promote culture.

Constitutional rights and guarantees

as the right to access culture, freedom of artistic and cultural expression, and equal enjoyment of cultural goods and services.

According to Article 215, the State must ensure that everyone can fully exercise their cultural rights and can access the sources of Brazil's national culture. It also must support and encourage cultural expression, especially the traditions and practices of popular, Indigenous and Afro-Brazilian communities, as well as all other groups that have shaped Brazilian society. This shows the Constitution's commitment to recognizing Brazil as a plural and diverse society

Art. 215

“The state shall ensure to all the full exercise of the cultural rights and access to the sources of national culture and shall support and foster the appreciation and diffusion of cultural expressions.

Paragraph 1. The State shall protect the expressions of popular, [Indigenous] and Afro-Brazilian cultures, as well as those of other groups participating in the national civilization process.

(...)”

Cultural rights in Article 215 has two dimensions:

It is a **duty of the State** to protect cultural heritage and cultural expressions.

It is also a **right of every person** to enjoy culture and demand access to cultural life.

Reference:
Renê Iarley da Rocha Marques, O sistema de garantias no Brasil para a defesa dos direitos culturais dos povos indígenas. São Paulo, Dialética, 2024.

Art. 216

“The Brazilian cultural heritage consists of the assets of a material and immaterial nature, taken individually or as a whole, which bear reference to the identity, action and memory of the various groups that form the Brazilian society, therein included:

I – forms of expression;

II – ways of creating, making and living;

III – scientific, artistic and technological creations;

IV – works, objects, documents, buildings and other spaces intended for artistic and cultural expressions;

V – urban complexes and sites of historical, natural, artistic, archaeological, paleontological, ecological and scientific value.

Paragraph 1. The Government shall, with the cooperation of the community, promote and protect the Brazilian cultural heritage, by means of inventories, registers, vigilance, monument protection decrees, expropriation and other forms of precaution and preservation.

(...)”

Article 216 explains what makes up Brazil's cultural heritage, which includes both material (tangible) and immaterial (intangible) elements that express the identity, memory and traditions of the country's many social groups.

What is cultural heritage?

Cultural heritage does not refer simply to objects or old buildings. Instead, it is the result of human actions and choices. It involves a continuous process in which societies select, preserve, protect and pass on certain material and immaterial elements that they consider valuable. The word "heritage" is used by analogy with what happens in families, where goods are passed from one generation to the next. In the cultural sense, this "inheritance" includes not only economic value but also symbolic, historical and emotional meanings.

Reference:
Cecilia Londres, "O patrimônio histórico na sociedade contemporânea", Revista Escritos, v.1, 2007.

Cultural heritage is therefore more than a collection of things, it is a **collective process of memory-making**. Communities and social groups decide what is important to remember, protect and transmit to future generations. This may include monuments, artworks, landscapes and objects, but also languages, celebrations, knowledge, beliefs, music, food traditions and many other forms of cultural expression. Through this shared process, cultural heritage helps shape a group's identity and strengthens its connection with the past, present and future.

Reference:
Cecilia Londres, "O patrimônio histórico na sociedade contemporânea", Revista Escritos, v.1, 2007.

Colombia

Cultural rights in Colombia are understood as essential for strengthening social cohesion, a sense of belonging, respect for life and diversity, and stronger community ties. They are considered collective rights because they create the conditions for creative expression, for maintaining social practices that shape memory and identity, and for giving meaning to cultural heritage and artistic forms.

Colombia's 1991 Constitution marked a turning point by recognising the country as multi-ethnic and multicultural. It enshrines specific cultural rights and incorporates international human rights norms through the "bloc of constitutionality." This constitutional model reflects the long struggles of Indigenous peoples and Afro-descendant communities for recognition, participation and the preservation of their worldviews, beliefs and cultural systems.

Art. 1 of Ley 397 de 1997

“The State guarantees ethnic and linguistic groups, black and Raizal communities, and indigenous peoples the right to preserve, enrich, and disseminate their identity and cultural heritage, to generate knowledge about them according to their own traditions, and to benefit from an education that ensures these rights.”

The General Culture Law (1997) thus strengthens this vision by guaranteeing the right of ethnic and linguistic communities to preserve, enrich and share their cultural identity and heritage, and to receive an education that supports these rights. It also establishes principles rooted in human rights, interculturality, pluralism, and tolerance.

Reference:
Miniterio de Cultural de Colombia, Revisión conceptual. Bogota,
2022.

In this framework, the Colombian Constitutional Court has recognized **biocultural rights**.

What is biocultural rights?

Biocultural rights are based on the idea that people, their cultures, and the natural environment are deeply connected. The term biocultural is used to show that humans have always interacted with nature, sometimes protecting ecosystems by respecting natural cycles, and sometimes harming them by ignoring those limits. Many Indigenous peoples and local communities hold knowledge that helps maintain both cultural traditions and the health of the environment.

Biocultural rights bring together different existing rights, such as the rights to identity, land, culture, and the environment, by recognising that cultural diversity and biological diversity depend on one another. For many Indigenous groups, culture, territory, and nature cannot be separated. These rights strengthen their ability to defend their lands, ways of life, and knowledge systems.

Reference:

Sören Koch, Esmeralda Colombo, and Catalina Vallejo Piedrahíta. “Derechos De La Naturaleza En La Cultura jurídica Noruega: ¿ser O No Ser?”. *Naturaleza y Sociedad. Desafíos Medioambientales*, no. 4, 2022.

Sentencia T-622/16

Biocultural rights are the rights of ethnic and Indigenous communities to manage and protect their lands and natural resources according to their own laws, traditions, and customs. These lands are where their culture, traditions, and way of life develop, and they are based on a special relationship with the environment and its biodiversity. These rights recognise that nature, natural resources, and culture are deeply connected—they depend on each other and cannot be understood separately.

At the heart of this approach is the idea that nature and culture are linked, and that human diversity is part of the natural world and expresses itself in many different ways of life. From this perspective, protecting biodiversity also means protecting the ways of life and cultures of the communities that live in and care for these ecosystems.

A bio-socio-cultural approach

A bio-socio-cultural approach emphasises that the connection between nature and culture cannot be understood without considering society. In fact, communities and social practices are essential in shaping and maintaining the relationship nature–culture. Culture, understood as a way of life, develops through shared knowledge, traditions, and activities within a community, which guide how people interact with the environment and use natural resources. Without the social dimension, the nature-culture link cannot exist, because it is the community that observes, interprets, and interacts with nature.

This approach highlights that biodiversity, cultural diversity, and social life are deeply interconnected. Protecting ecosystems is therefore not only an environmental concern but also a social and cultural one.

Reference:
Liliana Lizarazo-Rodriguez, Alice Lopes Fabris, Doreen Montag. Indigenous peoples as trustees of forests: a bio-socio-cultural approach to international law. *Int Environ Agreements*, 2024.

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